

Bakerwal goat: The robust goat breed of Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract

Bakerwal goat is an important goat genetic resource of Jammu and Kashmir, reared by nomadic tribe scattered in the Pir Panjal Himalayan Mountains of South Asia. The goat is scattered in hilly tracts of Poonch, Jammu, Rajouri, Udhampur and Kathua of Jammu and Kashmir. The breed originated from the valley of the Hazara district. The presence of long hair distributed uniformly throughout body of this goat in particular on neck region, abdomen, hind limbs and tail is its characteristic feature along with its horn pattern. Owing to this body coat of long coarse hairs these goats are well adapted to high altitudes and rocky terrains. This goat breed is highly variable with respect to its morphological and production traits. The overall estimates of 49.14 kg (range 35 to 81 kg) for adult body weight and 9.54 cm and 24.55 cm for ear length and width were observed in this goat. The males attain higher body weights at different ages. However, male animal is sold for meat at younger ages. The slaughter age for males is 1.5 to 2.5 years whereas in females it is higher. The overall estimates for body height of 80.65 cm, chest girth of 78.57 cm, paunch girth of 86.07 cm and body length of 74.55 cm was observed in this goat. It is concluded that **Bakerwal** is a robust goat and tall breed of goat of Jammu and Kashmir.

Introduction

Goats are important species in the small ruminants and second largest species in livestock category and contribute in the production of milk after cattle and buffaloes. As per 20th Livestock census, 26.40% of the livestock population is Goat. Rearing of goats is a traditional practice in Jammu and Kashmir. The tribals viz *Bakerwals*, *Gaddies* and *Changpas* have developed perfect professionalism in sheep & goat rearing. Goat is principally reared for meat, milk & fiber (Pashmina and Mohair), hide and skin. It also provides raw materials for many processing industries, of which leather is the most significant. This accounts for considerable employment and even export earnings. Goat commonly acknowledged as “**The poor man’s cow**” plays a vital

role in improving the socio-economic profile of poor rural masses, which depend for their sustenance on this animal. Farmers with marginal grazing lands rear goats as a source of livelihood. Changthangi, Malra, non-descript goats reared in Kashmir valley (Rather et al., 2020), Purgi (Alam et al., 2021) and Bakerwal are important goat genetic resources of Jammu and Kashmir. Bakarwal is a nomadic tribe based in the Pir Panjal and Himalayan mountains of South Asia. They are mainly goatherds and shepherds and are called as Dhangar in rest of India.

Origin, Distribution and breeding tract

The goat is scattered in hilly tracts of Poonch, Jammu, Rajouri, Udhampur and Kathua of Jammu and Kashmir. The breed originated from the valley of the Hazara district. They are also found in the North West Frontier Province of Pakistan. The goat is named for its main home Kaghan valley.

Synonyms

The Synonyms for this goat are Kaghani and Phari goat.

Utility of breed

The **Bakerwal** breed of goat is robust and large sized breed (adult body weight 35 to 81 kg) which plays an imperative role in livelihood and agrarian economics of Jammu province in particular Poonch, Jammu, Rajouri, Raise, Udhampur and Kathua districts. The breed is being used by the farmers for meat as well as milk production.

Strength/ weakness of the breeding tract

- Farmers have very good experience in rearing livestock since long
- Despite being a strong contributor to the agrarian economy and livelihoods of the poorest segments of the society, this breed of goat is neglected
- Availability of pure organic meat
- Limited or no access to veterinary care
- Low reproductive efficiency of the flocks
- Lack of technology to improve pasturelands and productive of this goat breed
- Inaccessibility in some of pasturelands
- Lack of technologies for processing and marketing goat products
- Lack of elite breeding bucks
- Random mating in flocks is practiced
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Tribe responsible for rearing of Bakerwal goat

The Bakerwal goat is mainly reared by Bakerwal tribe. The Bakarwal is a nomadic tribe inhabiting the Pir Panjal and Himalayan mountains of South Asia. They are mainly goatherds and shepherds called as Dhangar in rest of India (Choudhary et al., 2018). They have developed perfect professionalism in Sheep & Goat rearing (Alam et al. 2021), practice transhumance pastoralism, that involves cyclic movements from lowlands to highlands, to take advantage of seasonally available pastures at different elevations in Himalayas (Ara, 2005). Further the tribe is socially, educationally, economically and politically backward (Choudhary et al., 2018).

Characteristic feature

The style and presence of long hair distributed uniformly throughout body of this goat in particular on neck region, abdomen, hind limbs and tail is its characteristic feature along with its horn pattern (Fig 1 and 2).

Fig 1, 2 and 3 horn pattern and style of long hair of Bakerwal goat

Physical and morphometric traits of Bakerwal goat

Bakarwal goat is large, strong and robust in appearance. Physical and morphometric traits of Bakerwal goat are presented below.

Body coat

Bakerwal goat goats possess body coat of long coarse hairs of different colours. Owing to this body coat of long coarse hairs these goat are well adapted to high altitudes.

Color

The animals of Bakerwal goat breed are usually white, black, brown and grey. However, animals with mixed colors of white, black, brown and grey are mostly observed. Further, some animals with patches of white with black colour are also common. The color pattern of Bakerwal goat breed is reflected by Fig 1 to 5.

Fig 4 and 5.

Head profile

The head profile of Bakerwal goat is convex. They possess narrow face and a quite mobile lower lip. The head length (cm; the length from the point of poll up to the tip of upper lip) of 6.25, 7.75, 8.50, 9.00 and 9.54 at birth, three months, six months, twelve months and above 12 months age was observed in this goat. Males have higher estimates than females.

Horn shape and length

The goat possesses long, upward and laterally directed spiral horns (Fig 1 and 2). The horn length increases with age. Aged animals possess longer horns than younger animals. Some individuals of this breed are polled also (Fig 3). The horn length (cm; The length from base to the tip of the horn) vary from 25 to 40 cm in adult animals.

Ears

These goats usually possess long and drooping ears. However, small, rudimentary, folded and straight ears are not uncommon. These goats have average ear length and breadth of 24.55 cm (range 20 to 25.50) and 9.86 cm (range 7.55 to 11.55 cm).

Fig 6: Rudimentary ears Fig 7: Folded ears Fig 7: Folded and straight Fig 8: Long and drooping ears

Beard

Moat animals of breed possess beard (Fig 7 and 9).

Fig 9: Goat with well-developed Beard

Wattles

Wattles really observed in individuals of this breed.

Body height

The height of uppermost point of withers from the ground when the animal is in straight and standing on all its four limbs. Average body height (cm) of 33.63, 68.75, 71.75, 75.75 and 80.65 at birth, weaning, 6 months, 12 months and in adult animals, respectively was recorded in Bakarwal goat in the present study.

Chest girth

Chest girth is a circumferential measurement taken around the chest just behind the front legs and withers. Average body height (cm) of 31.43, 61.25, 65.00, 72.5 and 78.57 at birth, weaning, 6 months, 12 months and in adult animals, respectively was recorded in Bakarwal goat in the present study.

Body length

Average body length (cm) of 29.00, 60.00, 70.10, 72.25 and 74.55 at birth, weaning, 6 months, 12 months and in adult animals, respectively was recorded in Bakarwal goat in the present study.

Paunch girth

Paunch girth is a circumferential measurement taken around the paunch just before the hind legs. Average paunch girth (cm) of 29.58, 65.00, 68.75, 73.55 and 86.07 at birth, weaning, 6

months, 12 months and in adult animals, respectively was recorded in Bakarwal goat in the present study.

Tail length

The distance from the base (sacro-coccygeal articulation) to the tip of tail was considered as tail length. Average tail length of 185 to 25 cm was observed in this goat.

Body weight

Average body weight of 3.00 kg, 15.00 kg, 22 kg, 30, kg, 49.14 at birth, weaning, 6 months, 12 months and in adult animals, respectively was recorded in Bakarwal goat in the present study. The average adult body weight of 49.14 kg with range of 35 to 81 kg was observed in present study. The males were heavier than females at all stages of life cycle. Therefore, the animals possess excellent chevon confirmation and growth rate.

Breeding

Random natural breeding without any scientific intervention.

Slaughter ages

The males attain higher body weights at different ages. However, male animal are sold for meat at younger ages. The slaughter ages for males are 1.5 to 2.5 years.

Threats

Crossbreeding with Beetal in was observed

Important traits

.Important traits: Bakerwal goat is tall goat with huge structure when compared to other goat breeds of J&K. Bakerwal goat retains good feed conversion and reproductive efficiency.

Milk production: The goat produce on an average 0.75 litter milk for kids. The farmers rearing this goat proffer buffalo milk over goat milk. This may be one reason for low milk production of this goat. As no selection prefer might have been applied for selection for milk traits.

Management practices

This goat population is migratory in nature. They prefer rocky hilly landscapes and high altitudes. The goat is mainly reared for nutritious meat or chevon and milk. The most common diseases in the area are Peste des petitis ruminants, foot and mouth disease, pox and foot rot. The vaccinations are being practiced by the Department of Sheep Husbandry on regular basis for different infectious diseases. Age at first kidding of 18 to 24 months was observed. Gestation period ranges between 147 to 155 days and the Kidding Interval ranges between 190 to 365 days. The animals are shifted to highland pastures and one grazing ground to another in seasonal cycle from April to November of J and K by Bakarwals every year. However, the animals are managed at lowlands of Jammu division during winters. The animals are provided shelter for night hours in unscientific animal houses during winters. During winters animals are provided leaves, fodder made from naturally growing wild grasses, oats etc and maize in addition to grazing.

Constraints of goat rearing

Scarcity and high cost of feed and fodder during winter season and lack of scientific houses with provision of adequate light and ventilation for livestock are important constraints which constrain goat development. Random mating and lack scientific knowledge regarding management, feeding and breeding along with non-availability of good quality sires are also among constraints which impede goat development.

Interventions

Goat breeding farms need to be established by the Department of Sheep Husbandry in its breeding tracts on the lines as established for Kashmir Merino sheep to make this goat viable for both milk and chevon traits.

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